

Corporate Social Responsibilities of Banks, an Opportunity for Banks to Enhance and Retain their Customers

G. Nandini Prabhu¹ & P. S. Aithal²

¹Research Scholar, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University,
Mangalore, India

Orcid ID: 0000-0002-3187-0821; E-mail: prabhunandini25@gmail.com

²Professor, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

Orcid ID: 0000-0002-4691-8736; E-mail: psaithal@gmail.com

Author Contact Number: +919741411829

Abstract

Purpose: The banking sector in India's service industry sector aids the country's economy by raising deposits and offering credit to other businesses, industrial sectors, and individuals. The banking sector in India's service industry sector aids the country's economy by raising deposits and offering credit to other businesses, industrial sectors, and individuals. In accordance with a recent government regulation, public banks are required to make a voluntary contribution to a corporate social responsibility fund, while private banks are mandated to make a mandatory contribution of 2% of profit for social service activities to meet a multiplicity of collective requirements. It is curious to read how Indian banks have wisely utilised CSR funding. It would be motivating to compare the CSR programs of a few Indian public and private banks to discover how cleverly they have increased organizational business benefits. This study identifies and analyzes a variety of social responsibility programs offered by Indian financial firms. The data and information were obtained from the websites of the selected banks, bank prose from a variety of sources, bank statements, and related case studies. In order to develop CSR policy and oversee CSR programs, the government has mandated that companies with profits of 500 crores or more form a CSR team of at least three executives and one separate manager. Based on a study of CSR initiatives among private sector banks and public sector banks, it was found that the private sector banks prioritized delivering immediate assistance to their customer services, whereas public banks gave their brand-building efforts indirect backing. As a result, both categories of banks were able to gain from improved client satisfaction and, separately, the promotion of their services to underserved segments of the population. This research report assesses how private and public banks use the CSR money to keep and grow their client base.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), CSR strategy, Public and Private Banks, Customer retention, ABCD analysis,

Introduction :

Banks provide a range of services, such as loans, credit and debit cards, digital wealth management, and even personal care, to entice more consumers. However, the bulk of commercial banks provide a few crucial modern services. Recent years have seen a substantial increase in the importance of CSR, particularly in the banking and financial sectors. More and more, banks and additional commercial institutions are encouraging environmentally and generally responsible financing, along with structured financing. Due to the rapid increase in environmental awareness and concern, the service sector cannot continue to focus exclusively on profit-making and must instead develop a strategy of offering green services that are advantageous to the environment. Banks in particular are increasingly forced to follow environmental regulation (Garriga, E., & Melé, D. (2004) [1]). To resuscitate a better tomorrow, several important changes must be implemented by developing some green movement guidelines. Due to the standardization of the banking sector, financial institutions find it challenging to deliver the high-quality services necessary to attract and keep consumers. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is a planned concern that has long been acknowledged as helping organizations increase customer retention.

2. RELATED WORK :

Several research have looked at the association between customer faithfulness and product attentiveness. Numerous studies have looked at how CSR influences a range of characteristics, including word-of-mouth, interactive, respects, purposes, emotional linking, in-store purchasing, and brand identification. (Bhattacharya and Luo (2006) [2]), studied Fortune 500 issues and found a connection between CSR and customer happiness. As a result of their findings, consumer pleasure is mediated by the relationship between CSR and business market value.

The responsibility for monitoring the activities of the nation's financial institutions should fall on Indian banks. The economic system should provide for the requirements of the populace and vice versa. The output and distribution system's overall socioeconomic worth has increased. Additionally, it's thought that banks who comply with CSR have better benefit excellence and liquidity ratios as well as better capital management skills (Keffas and Briggs, 2011) [3]).

The biggest irony is how slowly CSR has advanced in India, despite the fact that it began there many years ago and that the Indian government has regularly been seen passing the laws known as the Guidelines for CSR activities. Despite the motivation, there has been a noticeable trend in the Indian commercial sector to promote initiatives that are advantageous to both the environment and society.. Das, S. K. (2012).[4]

Scale and profitability of banks have a significant impact on CSR. The mainstream of banks did not reveal their projects on their websites, despite the fact that the contemporary banks whether private or public were strong performers in CSR (Khan, H. U. Z. (2010) [5]).

According to the report, CSR improves any institution's reputation over time and brings about financial gain. According to Holder-Webb et al. (2009), a company can use CSR to acquire a competitive advantage, boost stakeholder trust, and establish a solid long-term reputation. The company's reputation, goodwill, and financial performance are all negatively impacted by CSR, according to the most recent CSR literature, according to Gautam and Singh (2010). CSR has allegedly been a hot topic for research for a long time (Holder-Webb,et.,al (2009) [6]).

CSR was only a requirement for businesses to provide societal benefits. Even though the precise definition of CSR is not provided anywhere, claim that CSR still has several benefits for the banking industry. According to Attila CSR is the best option for integrating moral and ethical concepts in the banking sector given the current economic climate (McWilliams, A., & Siegel, D. S. (2011) [7]).

It was stated that CSR varies throughout time, across businesses, across companies, and across regions (Welford, R. (2007) [8]).

According to Burianová and Paulík (2014), Social responsibility and ethics are encouraged by the adoption of CSR and moral standards in the banking industry, which have developed into effective marketing tools for attracting stakeholders. The concept of CSR was established by State Bank of India at the beginning of 1973 under the aegis of Innovative Banking, which covered both banking and non-banking efforts. The bank first focused on the marginalised and less fortunate sections of society by giving them a chance to improve their financial situation. With its non-banking activities, the bank focused on regional projects that promote efficient public administration, including health fairs, blood drives, educational programmes, participation in regional celebrations, etc.. With the aid of Community Service Banking Schemes, the bank now fulfils its CSR obligations to the community while simultaneously acting as a responsible corporate citizen. CSR acknowledges that businesses have a accountability to comportment themselves in a socially responsible style (Burianová, L., & Paulík, J. (2014) [9]).

Dusuki and Dar (2005) discovered numerous factors, including increased market pressure on social and moral issues, uniformity pressures from various governing authorities, expanded media influence, and others, underlying the growing prominence of CSR initiatives. however, noted that, particularly in the banking sector, CSR efforts in underdeveloped nations are not as vigorous (Dusuki, A. W., & Dar, H. (2005) [10]).

Table-1 Related work on Corporate Social Responsibilities Activities.

S.No.	Areas	Focus	outcomes	References
1	Corporate socially responsible initiatives,	According to their study, The reputation of an institution is significantly influenced by CSR, which eventually also creates economic value.	The novel study approach proposed in this paper may help to clarify CSR and encourage banks to implement it.	[11].
2	Will green CSR encourage innovation?	By putting in place CSR programs that are tied to the market, the banking industry can improve its standing and financial success with partners. (Frenkel & Scott, 2002).	Business leaders should institutionalize workplace green behavior at the individual, team, and organizational levels, according to the report. Green management and csr strategies must be perfectly aligned.	[12].
4	Corporate governance	Banks concentrate on investment accountability and responsibility to attain this goal (Kurtz, 2008). (KPMG, 2005). Particularly, National Bank provided through investment initiatives in the area of renewable energy (National Bank, 2012).	This study focussed on CSR, it must be assumed that society and economic interests are so linked that it is necessary from an economic perspective to satisfy societal demands.	[13].
5	International Journal of Enterprise Information	Due to the crucial role that employees play, a bank wants to focus on the workplace when adopting CSR activities. Banks must enhance their	The study provides comprehensive and deep gaining knowledge about CSR in the banking industry by reading several	[14].

		environment if they want to draw in quality workers and boost employee output. (Bhattacharya, Sen, & Korschun, 2008; Muthuri, Matten, & Moon, 2009)	empirical and theoretical research papers and articles from around the globe.	
6	Financial Performance of Indian Banks and Corporate Social Responsibility	Banks typically acknowledge that employee human rights fall outside the purview of labor laws. All policies and practices put in place by the bank reflect the CSR principles concentrating on the market.	The paper has some ramifications for scholars, professionals, and decision-makers. In the academic setting.	[15].
7	A Survey of Indian Nationalized Banks Based on Evidence	In this paper "CSR means companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and their interaction with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis."	The results of this study reveal to managers and executives in banks that banks engaging in CSR activities may gain from socially responsible acts in terms of employee morale, client loyalty, favourable bank position, etc.	[16].
8	Analysis of CSR activities of banks	The author illustrated how a business has needs for self-actualization, esteem, safety, and physiology needs.	Strong CSR may consequently help banks' connections to their customers and shareholders, as well as boost their ability to access funding sources and reduce investment risk.	[17].
9	Indian banking sectors CSR reporting and practices.	CSR is often most directly shaped by the Socio-economic priorities in which banks operate and the development priorities this creates	Bank leaders from developing to developed countries should adjust their attitude toward CSR and adopt CSR programs.	[18].
10	Indian banking sectors Corporate social responsibility	International standardisation is a means of self-regulation, but it is crucial for businesses to successfully implement CRS standards, not just the portions that align with their interests.	This study reveals that CSR reporting in the area has improved both in terms of number and quality on a strictly voluntary basis.	[19].
11	SBI and ICICI Bank's CSR Programs	This study explored how CSR may be applied to achieve a competitive advantage, increase trust with stakeholders, and build a strong previous sets for a business.	Due to its unique regulatory requirements and alleged lack of significant environmental impact, the banking industry is frequently left out of CSR studies. This study enhances to the body of existing information in this	[20].

			regard. The two-tier system is the subject of this study, which is the first of its kind.	
12	CSR in private and public banks	Analysis of the corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities carried out by Indian commercial banks is the original study principal goal of this study..	In this essay, it was noted how private sector banks and international banks continue to fall behind in CSR initiatives.	[21].

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

- (1) To find the Green Corporate social responsibility (GCSR) activities of some of the selected private and public banks in India.
- (2) To analyze employee engagement in CSR practices of the selected Indian banks to retain their customers.
- (3) To identify the customers retention strategy of banks through suitable CSR activities.
- (4) To analyze ABCD analysis of CSR activities of the banking industry.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

The analysis presented in this paper is based on secondary information obtained from bank's website as well as academic works presented at conferences and journals. Knowledge about CSR initiatives is compiled and compared between private and public banks using published data, such as financial statements of public and private commercial banks.

6. THE GREEN SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE BANKS :

In order to secure durable growth, green banking should be given more public recognition; businesses may then employ it as a CSR policy. Additionally, the green banking idea loans money to projects including renewable energy and energy efficiency and businesses that aim to conduct more ecologically approachable daily operations. It alludes to banking practices that are more environmentally friendly and that lessen both internal and external carbon footprints. Although it isn't frequently considered, banking exposes people to pollution. In relations of increased energy usage, such as lighting, air conditioning, and paper consumption. It has a considerable control on the environment. As a consequence, implementing CSR principles into business operations is crucial to the economy's long-term health. Banks can be described as corporate citizens who, like any other company, industry, or individual, have a social obligation. The term "green banking" highlights the importance of the environment Customers, on the other hand, have a quite better approach toward corporate social responsibility. Furthermore, customers may be more sensitive to careless behavior than to firm action that is socially responsible. While outlining the explanation, customers must be explicit about the company's struggles towards social responsibilities (Wanderley, L. S. O., Lucian, R., Farache, F., & de Sousa Filho, J. M. (2008) [22]).

Table 2: Green banking practices of banks in India (Nandini Prabhu, G., & Aithal, P. S. (2021) [23]).

Serial No	Public Sector Banks	Private Sector Banks
1	State Bank of India	ICICI

2	Punjab National Bank	HDFC
3	Bank of Baroda	Axis Bank
4	Canara Bank	Yes Bank
5	Central Bank	Kotak Mahindra Bank
6	IDBI Bank	IndusInd Bank

7 EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT PRACTICES OF THE SELECTED INDIAN BANKS TO RETAIN THEIR CUSTOMERS

Employee involvement refers to an organization's efforts to completely incorporate its workers into its strategies, practices, and policies, such as welfare and sustainability initiatives. Employees at both private and public banks agree that the bank agrees workers to engage in social activities in an equal percentage of cases. Banks must actively participate in social activities if they are to benefit society. No public bank employee is against the rules controlling bank issue. No employee of a publicly traded bank is opposed to the bank's continued support of corporate social responsibility. Most employees of equally public and commercial banks trust that banking is a means of generating wealth. Employees at both banks who work in the private sector (99%) and public sector (12/13) agree that each bank should be responsible for corporate social responsibility. Employees from the public and private sectors contribute to CSR budgets. Below is a list of the practices of various CSR employees.

(1) The SBI staff members are motivated to help the community in any way they can. Among these are additional CSR employee engagement activities, an objective and transparent IT-driven presentation appraisal system, and the career progression system (CPS).

(2) Bank employees are encouraged to volunteer their time and talents as part of the "Corporate Volunteering Program." Employees of the bank have taken part in projects this year that include educational aid organizations, English-language programs, and helping to organize special events for the needy. Bank employees are encouraged to volunteer their time and talents as part of the "Corporate Volunteering Program." This year, bank personnel have taken part in projects such as helping to organize special events for the needy and working with educational aid groups and English-language classes.

(3) The bank makes a monthly contribution in an amount equivalent to what its employees make. 2500 people participated in the staff health program, and nine cities hosted the internal talent competition (Aithal, P. S. (2016) [24]).

8. IDENTIFY THE CUSTOMERS RETENTION STRATEGY OF THESE BANKS THROUGH SUITABLE CSR ACTIVITIES

Consumers are largely impacted by CSR programs in terms of perceived value, trust, and dedication, which leads to higher levels of satisfaction and loyalty. Few studies have observed at the joining between customer trustworthiness and product consciousness, despite the impact of CSR being explored on factors like word-of-mouth, consumer communication, attitudes, goals, emotional linking, in-store shopping, and trademark consciousness. An analysis of 503 firms revealed a connection between CSR and customer happiness. According to their research, the connection between CSR and firm arcade worth mediates customer satisfaction. In other words, customer happiness constructs lost significance as CSR's influence on market value increased. However, the study found that CSR did not always lead to client happiness. The studies mentioned above found that despite the well-known status of client happiness in the promotion literature, academics have

paid less attention to the function of CSR in determining customer pleasure. Keeping consumers has boosted demand on the banking system in the current situation. However, a problem that banks encounter is a shortage of customers as a result of the fierce rivalry from competing banks (Garriga, E., & Melé, D. (2004) [25]). Studies reveal, however, that the introduction of foreign banks has improved the Indian banking sector, with new, better-offering technologies and services giving banks a wealth of opportunities to attract and keep customers.

Client retention describes the measures that businesses and organizations use to prevent clients from leaving. In order to assist businesses keep as many customers as possible, customer retention strategies are developed, generally through brand and customer loyalty programs.

(1) Implement a customer feedback loop.

Based on user feedback and suggestions, the customer feedback loop is a strategy for ongoing product improvement. It entails giving clients a fair response when they submit comments.

(2) Maintain a customer communication calendar.

1. Build a relationship. Take the time to be professional and personable with your customers.
2. Listen to customers. Active listening is a skill like any other, and you need to practice it.
3. Use analogies.
4. Develop customer service standards.
5. Resolve disputes quickly.

(3) Start a customer education program.

Improved customer education, which may occur through a range of channels and take many various forms, is one of the best methods to increase brand power and customer loyalty. Customer education may be created to help clients use the products, for instance, if the bank makes or sells green banking products.

(4) Build trust with customers.

The development of trusting relationships with customers is essential for a company's success. Increasing client trust is one way to improve customer interactions. If the bank wants to increase the number of new clients it attracts and grow its clientele, it should put its primary focus on gaining customer confidence. This article will discuss the importance of gaining customer trust as well as the seven essential actions a bank can take to achieve so. Trust-building is a customer-centered strategy that can benefit businesses in a number of ways. Customer trust is important for businesses because it can help them attract and retain loyal customers. The ability of a company to retain consumers has a direct impact on its performance because doing so can increase sales. Building consumer trust will also give the bank the ability to convert devoted clients into brand ambassadors—people who promote the firm and draw in new clients allowing it to expand its clientele and enhance its reputation (Patjoshi, P. K., & Nayak, U. (2020) [26]).

(5) Offer unique services (Biometrics)

As fingerprint scanners become more and more popular among smartphone users, banks are starting to embrace the technology for their own mobile apps and payment solutions. Biometrics provide an extra degree of security for banking customers who are particularly concerned about fraud. One piece of advice is to adopt as many security measures as possible.

9. ABCD ANALYSIS OF CSR ACTIVITIES OF THE BANKING INDUSTRY :

ABCD analysis is a renewed analysis framework that was developed systematically in this century and is utilized in many scientific works in various formats. ABCD analysis is a qualitative or quantitative method of analyzing a concept, system, strategy, product, service, or other aspect of an

organization by stakeholders. ABCD listing is a qualitative discussion of a given thing that involves identifying and describing the entity's advantages, benefits, restrictions, and downsides from the perspectives of various stakeholders. The advantages, benefits, limits, and downsides of CSR Activities in the Banking Industry from the bank's perspective are outlined below, based on observations of material obtained from the websites of the banks under deliberation (Hu, V. I., & Scholtens, B. (2014) [27]).

(a) Advantages :

- Develops different business images for various sections;
- Conveys real aids to civilization as a whole;
- Produces formed operative exuberance and higher efficiency levels;
- Makes banks more conscious of their potential part in society;
- Create self assured promotional and expanded brand credit.

(b) Benefits :

- CSR increases employee engagement;
- CSR enhances financial results;
- CSR helps local and worldwide populations;
- Helps to achieve the UN's 17 Sustainable Development Goals
- Expands savings possibilities
- Offers new ways to contribute to society.
- Increases consumer loyalty and retention.
- Corporate social responsibility promotes employer branding.

© Constraints :

- A lack of community participation in CSR activities.
- The essential to shape local capacity.
- Transparency issues.
- Absence of well-organized non-governmental organizations available for partnership.
- The degree to which the services supplied are visible,
- Limited understanding of CSR creativities.

(d) Disadvantages :

- The initial is that when a company pursues out and progresses traditions to operate that are different from their usual way of doing things in demand to encounter CSR standards, they must remuneration special charges for doing so, which can be costly for the company.
- The second way these expenditures are negative is that they carry with them a slew of other costs that a company must cover, such as worker training, investing in specific social programs, and guaranteeing environmental safety.

10. FINDINGS:

1. We conclude from the study's findings that CSR has been effective in boosting green banking products and ensuring consumer satisfaction.
2. All sectors of the economy have benefited from the government's recent ruling to require corporations to contribute 2% of their profits towards CSR.

11. SUGGESTIONS :

It would like to suggest the following measures in order to make CSR more effective and operational in banking sector.

- The government must launch awareness campaigns at all levels, from the grassroots to the corporate.
- Government must include corporate interests in all important social choices.
- Every corporation should prioritise economic development, and they should be urged to take ownership under difficult circumstances.

12. CONCLUSION :

It may be inferred that both sector banks are making an effort to interact meaningfully with their clients through CSR initiatives. It's possible that not all Public Sector bank branches regularly implemented CSR programmes to engage with customers. In addition, consumers of Public Bank are pleased with some of the expressive programmes offered by the bank, such as gatherings for customers or events like Free Medicinal Site, greeting cards and SMS sent on special occasions like anniversaries and centenaries, etc. It is crucial to keep in mind when creating CSR initiatives, as these projects demand cautious arrangement and execution procedures at the same time. This is explained by the fact that a single CSR programme may or may not be as effective and successful for different firms, depending on how it is implemented.

According to government regulations, businesses with annual profits of 500 crores or more are required to form a CSR team with at least three administrators and one independent superintendent to create CSR policies and manage CSR initiatives. Based on a evaluation of CSR activities between private and public sector banks, it was discovered that private sector banks' CSR efforts were concentrated on actively funding their customer services, whereas public banks' CSR efforts were implicitly condoning their brand-building initiatives. As a result, both types of banks were able to benefit from increased client pleasure and the advancement of their amenities to underserved areas of society.

References:

- [1] Garriga, E., & Melé, D. (2004). Corporate social responsibility theories: Mapping the territory. *Journal of business ethics*, 53(1), 51-71

DOI;<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/B:BUSI.0000039399.90587.34>

- [2] Luo, X., & Bhattacharya, C. B. (2006). Corporate social responsibility, customer satisfaction, and market value. *Journal of marketing*, 70(4), 1-18.

DOI :<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1509/jmkg.70.4.001>

- [3] Keffas, G., & Olulu-Briggs, O. V. (2011). Corporate social responsibility: How does it affect the financial performance of banks? Empirical evidence from US, UK and Japan. *Journal of management and corporate governance*, 3(1), 8-26.

DOI; <https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/83337374/>

[4] Das, S. K. (2012). Customer relationship management in banking sector: a comparative study of SBI and other nationalised commercial banks in India. *Arth Prabandh: A Journal of Economics and Management*, 1(6), 2278-0629.[4]

DOI ;<https://5y1.org/download/0eb717298ba5664bd2992f04e1cda731.pdf>

[5] Khan, H. U. Z. (2010). The effect of corporate governance elements on corporate social responsibility (CSR) reporting: Empirical evidence from private commercial banks of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 52(2), 82-109.

DOI :<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/17542431011029406/full/html>

[6] Holder-Webb, L., Cohen, J. R., Nath, L., & Wood, D. (2009). The supply of corporate social responsibility disclosures among US firms. *Journal of business ethics*, 84(4), 497-527

DOI :<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10551-008-9721-4>

[7] McWilliams, A., & Siegel, D. S. (2011). Creating and capturing value: Strategic corporate social responsibility, resource-based theory, and sustainable competitive advantage. *Journal of management*, 37(5), 1480-1495.

DOI :<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0149206310385696>

[8] Welford, R. (2007). Corporate governance and corporate social responsibility: Issues for Asia. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 14(1), 42-51.

DOI :<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/csr.139>

[9] Burianová, L., & Paulík, J. (2014). Corporate Social Responsibility in commercial banking-a case study from the Czech Republic. *Journal of competitiveness*, 6(1), 50-70

DOI :<https://doi.org/10.7441/joc.2014.01.04>

[10] Dusuki, A. W., & Dar, H. (2005, November). Does corporate social responsibility pay off? An empirical examination of stakeholder perspectives. In *2nd International Conference on Business Performance*, 22(1)
DOI: [10.24297/ijmit.v4i3.4544](https://doi.org/10.24297/ijmit.v4i3.4544)

[11] Sharma, E., & Mani, M. (2013). Corporate social responsibility: An analysis of Indian commercial banks. *AIMA journal of Management & Research*, 7(1/4), 0974-497.

DOI :https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326295265_

[12] Soni, D., & Mehta, P. (2018). Employee Engagement in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): Reflection from Indian Banking Sector. *Journal of Strategic Human Resource Management*, 7(2), 40-47.

DOI :<http://www.publishingindia.com/jshrm/32>.

[13] Duggal, M. (2013). Profitability and productivity analysis of LIC housing finance limited and HDFC limited a comparative study. *Pranjana: The Journal of Management Awareness*, 16(1), 56-66

<https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.403.9436&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

[14] Kavitha, S. (2018). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): A Case Study of Axis Bank Foundation. *Ushus Journal of Business Management*, 17(1), 53-63

DOI :<https://journals.christuniversity.in/index.php/ushus/article/view/1923>

[15] Saxena, S. (2016). A comparative study of corporate social responsibility (CSR) of private and public sector banks. *World Wide Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 2(1), 21-23.

DOI :<http://wwjmr.com/upload/a->

- [16] Singh, N., Srivastava, R., & Rastogi, R. (2013). CSR practices & CSR reporting in Indian Banking Sector. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 3(12), 1-8.
DOI :<https://www.ijsrp.org/research-paper-1213/ijsrp-p2486.pdf>
- [17] Dhingra, D., & Mittal, R. (2014). CSR practices in Indian banking sector. *Global Journal of Finance and Management*, 6(9), 853-862.
DOI :https://www.ripublication.com/gjfm-spl/gjfmv6n9_08.pdf
- [18] Rocca, E., & Yashar, Y. (2018). A better Risk Management through the integration of CSR in bank processes. *BANCARIA*, 4(1), 57-62.
DOI :https://www.ripublication.com/gjfm-spl/gjfmv6n9_08.pdf
- [19] James, L. (2012). Prospects of CSR: An overview of 500 Indian companies. *The IUP Journal of Corporate Governance*, 11(4), 55-68.
DOI :https://www.researchgate.net/publication/255857820_
- [20] Hedge, S. (2020). CSR practices in state bank of India and its impact on creating loyal customers: A study in Mangaluru city; Karnataka. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(10), 291-299.
DOI :https://www.researchgate.net/publication/355182262_
- [21] Batra, R., & Bahri, A. (2018). Financial Performance and corporate social responsibility (CSR): empirical evidence from banks in India. *International Journal of Business Ethics in Developing Economies*, 7(2), 37-42.
DOI :<https://www.academia.edu/40428146>
- [22] Wanderley, L. S. O., Lucian, R., Farache, F., & de Sousa Filho, J. M. (2008). CSR information disclosure on the web: a context-based approach analysing the influence of country of origin and industry sector. *Journal of business ethics*, 82(2), 369-378.
- [23] Nandini Prabhu, G., & Aithal, P. S. (2021). A review based research agenda on green banking service practices through greencsr activities,6(2),204-230
DOI : [10.47992/ijmts.2581.6012.0165](https://doi.org/10.47992/ijmts.2581.6012.0165)
- [24] Aithal, P. S. (2016). Realization of Ideal Banking Concept using Ubiquitous Banking. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 2(1), 119-135.
DOI :<https://zenodo.org/record/164703>
- [25] Garriga, E., & Melé, D. (2004). Corporate social responsibility theories: Mapping the territory. *Journal of business ethics*, 53(1), 51-71.
DOI :<https://www.jstor.org/stable/25123282>
- [26] Patjoshi, P. K., & Nayak, U. (2020). Impact of CSR on Financial Performance: A Study on Banking Companies in India. *International Journal of Modern Agriculture*, 9(3), 953-962.
DOI :<https://www.google.com/search?q=%5B26%5D>
- [27] Hu, V. I., & Scholtens, B. (2014). Corporate social responsibility policies of commercial banks in developing countries. *Sustainable Development*, 22(4), 276-288.
DOI :<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/sd.1551>